

The Influence of Humor on the Effectiveness of Environmental Narratives*

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Abstract

In parallel with the growing urgency of a society capable of behaving in a sustainable manner, the need for an investment in communication strategies that promote responsible consumption in defense of the environment, expands. Fear is one of the most evoked emotions in campaigns within the context of promoting causes and values of general interest to society – social advertising -, yet, the impact of other stimuli in this context must be analyzed. This study focuses on the influence of the humorous tone on the effectiveness of advertising narratives of environmental nature. In order to fulfill this objective, two types of studies were conducted: a quantitative one, with the application of a questionnaire, and another qualitative, based on interviews to art directors from advertising agencies. The quantitative analysis allowed us to study two ads of different emotional tones, one dramatic and another humorous, regarding Attitude towards the ad, General attention to the ad, Recall, Intention to forward, and Behavioural intention, and some other effects were tested. The results demonstrated the effectiveness of the humorous narrative, although the dramatic one had shown superiority in almost all dimensions under study. In the end, the results from the quantitative analysis are discussed, integrating them with the insights extracted from the interviews.

Keywords: storytelling; humor; advertising; social marketing; environment; effectiveness

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Introduction

The core of the present study is the influence of humor on the effectiveness of environmental advertising narratives, that is, the possible effects of humor on advertising communicated in the form of a narrated story, addressing the environmental protection as its background.

One of the greatest adversities that humanity has faced throughout this century is the crisis in the balance of the environment, which has been an important factor in changing living standards, compromising future generations (Nellemann & Corcoran, 2010). Although concerns related to sustainability are not a recent issue, with policies within this scope being developed for decades, in the 21st century this has become a mainstream issue (Chen, 2010). In this context, advertising, as a characteristically persuasive tool, can take part in this positive movement towards improving the current environmental landscape, by influencing citizens' attitudes and behaviors.

Social marketing, an area of activity in the field of marketing, designed to influence a target audience to accept, reject, modify or abandon behavior in favor of individuals or society (Lee & Kotler, 2007), is applied in several sectors, among them health, social solidarity, civic education and prevention of the environment (Gonçalves, nd). The attempt to provoke fear has been a central aspect in most advertising messages comprised in the field of social marketing, however, the adoption of positive emotions, such as humor, enthusiasm, or love, can be an equally effective technique for these purposes (Hastings, Stead, & Webb, 2004). Advertising humor, in particular, has proven to be an excellent means of attracting audience attention, facilitating the memorization of communication, and creating connections with the brand (Akyuz, 2015).

Through a combination of qualitative and quantitative methodology, this research aims to answer the following starting question: what will be the influence of the humorous tone on the effectiveness of a pro-environmental advertising narrative? In this sense, in this study are addressed techniques to optimize advertising narratives developed in the context of social marketing. Capturing effective advertising tools that help consumers behave responsibly for the purpose of a sustainable development is an important step. To date, studies carried out with reference to humor in the context of environmental advertising are very limited, and the combination of humor with the advertising narrative and the environment is a matter yet to be explored. Given the subject on which this investigation is concerned, the specific objectives to be fulfilled are the following:

1. To study, regarding the piece of humorous communication under investigation, its effectiveness based on the analysis of factors - Attitude towards the advertisement, General attention, Recall and Intention to share -, as well as the effect of humor in specific;
2. To compare the humorous communication with the dramatic communication in terms of Attitude towards the ad, General attention, Recall, Intention to forward and Influence on the behavioral intention;

Communicating social ideas

Kotler and Zaltman (1971) defined the term “social marketing”, for the first time, as “the explicit use of marketing skills in order to help translate current social action efforts into more effectively thought out and communicated programs that provoke the desired responses of the audience ”(p.5). In this way, social marketers seek to change, in people, potentially dangerous attitudes to society in the short and long term (Kotler & Andreasen, 1996), as well as to make these altered attitudes last (Andreasen, 1995).

Social marketing is a concept linked to that of commercial marketing in terms of techniques and concepts, more specifically in terms of the studies undertaken to perceive the needs and desires of the target audience; the attempt to make the idea being sold something appealing; the ease and accessibility of converting motivations into actions; and the price of decision-making, which, in the case of social marketing, refers to the study of the cost-benefit ratio when considering the investment of money, time or energy in the subject in question (Kotler & Zaltman, 1971). Even so, these two practices differ from each other in terms of principles (Brites, 1998). Contrary to business-related marketing, in social marketing the objective is to benefit society in general, and not just that of the organization (Kotler & Andreasen, 1991).

Just as social marketing is distinguished from commercial marketing, a distinction is made between commercial and social advertising. When Kotler (1998) defined advertising as “any form, not personal, of presenting or promoting ideas, goods or services, paid for by an identified sponsor” (p.587), he referred to the existence of two approaches to take in actions communication: commercial advertising, related to the promotion of goods and services, integrated in the context of traditional marketing, and social advertising, related to the promotion of ideas, developed with the objective of transmitting causes.

In this sense, the term 'social advertising' can be understood as “the communicative activity of a persuasive, paid, intentional and interested character, which serves, through advertising means, concrete causes of social interest” (López, 2005, p. 266). The four major groups, in terms of thematic, associated with communicative actions of social advertising are: health and public and social well-being, marginalization and discrimination, international solidarity, and protection of the environment (López, 2005).

Despite the efforts made to achieve sustainability, it is difficult to make consumption reduction an appealing topic (Peattie & Peattie, 2009). Therefore, it is important to make communication engaging and act as a storyteller of modern times, associating this topic with another that makes people feel inspired, as other types of issues are generally more relevant to people, despite showing concern for the environment (United Nations Environment Program, 2005).

Storytelling: an advertiser weapon

Storytelling, defined by Pellowski (1991) as the art of telling a story, in prose or verse, transmitted from speech or singing, to a live audience, is a vital skill that has been extremely important since ancient times (Nossel, 2018). The first evidences of man's communication

are visual representations of stories in caves, created for the purpose of representing daily activities and cultural norms (Hurlburt & Voas, 2011). The transmission of information, through its report, guaranteed us survival, enabling the sharing of dangers and the direction to take to resist them (Nossel, 2018).

Man is a “storytelling animal” (Gottschall, 2012), who thinks in the form of a narrative, before going on to an analytical or argumentative analysis (Nossel, 2018), and who, living in the chaotic, disorderly and complex world where he lives, is constantly looking for clear and well-defined concepts, making use of stories to simplify the complexity and contradictions of life (Simmons, 2001).

Now, although traditionally associated with the presence of a person who persuades or reports (Weissenfeld, Abramova, & Krasnova, 2017), the practice of storytelling has evolved, having been widely used in several areas, including brand communication (Sobol, Quentile, & Sunwolf, 2004). The current trend of storytelling in marketing practices is due to the appearance of a 'dream society', that is, a society in which the functionality of products and services is taken for granted, providing an increase in sales from the appeal to consumers' emotions (Jensen, 2001). The current urgency of brands to tell appealing and attractive stories, shareable, relevant content that seeks to add value, is part of our times (Vaynerchuck, 2013), since today our ability to retain information is also much limited, generating that necessity (Ries & Trout, 2002).

The direct sale, or that made from the presentation of facts, is a largely manifested approach in promotion that communicate information about a product, having as its main focus its characteristics, attributes and benefits (Belch & Belch, 2015). Despite that, several studies allege that ads that make use of storytelling are more engaging, also resulting in more positive evaluations compared to more informative ads (Hong, Kang, & Hubbard, 2018; Adaval & Wyer, 1998).

A research carried out by Escalas (2004) made it possible to conclude that, since man naturally attributes meaning to his experiences through stories conceived by him, processing information depicted in a story format can be beneficial for the connections between people and brands, thus impacting positively consumers' behavioral intentions. These emotional connections are the consequence of positive feelings generated by the viewer's identification with the story, based on the characters, excluding the intrusiveness aspect characteristic of traditional advertising (Kim & Sullivan, 2019).

In the context of communicating social ideas, storytelling is a practice that begins to gain dominance, and vice versa. Non-governmental organizations, such as Greenpeace, adopt a narrative approach with images to point out how much man has been a harmful agent for planet Earth, encouraging people to observe the negative environmental conditions of today (Nayan, 2013). In a study related to the construction of consumer-brand connections, based on communication in a story format, Forman and Granitz (2015) came to the conclusion that the stories related to the concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) are those that all consumers want to listen.

Measuring the effectiveness of social marketing campaigns

Understanding the effectiveness of an advertising campaign is an asset in the sense that it helps advertising professionals to better channel their budget, as well as advertising agencies to measure the effectiveness of their primary service (Bendixen, 1993). Since there is no global measure capable of explaining the effectiveness of advertising, it becomes relevant to consider a series of methods and measures capable of acting towards a partial verification of the results (Corvi & Bonera, 2010).

Given that social marketing, as previously mentioned, is based on techniques used equally in commercial marketing activity (Andreasen, 1995; Kotler & Zaltman, 1971), to measure the effectiveness of a social communication campaign, it is relevant to consider some aspects covered in what is traditional advertising.

According to Colley (1961), the effects of an advertising piece must go through three dimensions: the cognitive, the affective and the behavioral. Within the cognitive dimension, attention is seen as an important indicator of the effectiveness of advertising communication (Wedel and Pieters, 2011; Rossiter and Percy, 2001), as well as the recall factor (Brasini, Freo, & Tassinari, 2011; Mehta & Purvis, 2006). In the affective field, the attitude towards an advertisement, defined by Bamoriya and Singh (2011) as the reaction to an advertising piece, which can be either favorable or not favorable, is a measuring instrument of enormous relevance (Mackenzie, Lutz, & Belch, 1986; Edell & Burke, 1984).

In addition to the advertising objective linked to “what we want the target audience to think, feel, believe or desire after receiving the advertising message”, there is also a behavioral objective, “which is what we want the target audience do it”, or who is influenced to do it (Gonçalves, sd, p.12). The intention to forward an advertisement by consumers, in an online environment, is considered by several professionals as a way of measuring the effectiveness of a piece of viral advertising (Thorbjørnsen, Ketelaar, Riet, & Dahlén, 2015), a term that designates an activity of promotion of brands, products or services, based on communication between people via the internet (Ketelaar, Janssen, Vergeer, & Reijmersdal, 2016). Furthermore, in the context of social marketing, behavioural intention, seen as the apparent probability of an individual being involved or adopting a certain behavior, is an important indicator to consider when assessing this dimension encompasses consumer action and behaviour (Ajzen, 2011).

Specifically, a piece of social advertising must be able to obey some crucial points. With the ultimate goal of influencing decision-making (Kotler & Zaltman, 1971), the ability to alert to a cause must be a basic principle of communication; second, it must be credible (Orozco, 2010; Petty & Cacioppo, 1996); thirdly, it must make the message well understood, since when well understood it will naturally manifest greater power to persuade (Petty & Cacioppo, 1984), as well as to affect memory, intentions and behaviors (Ratneshwar & Chaiken, 1991); fourthly, it must be able to attract the audience's attention to the matter, something that Greenpeace does through the use of planet Earth disturbing emotions (Nayan, 2013).

Thus, there are a number of aspects that express the success of a social marketing campaign, and this effectiveness will depend on several factors. The emotional tone of a message, specifically, affects both the formulation of thoughts and the generation of emotions in relation to an advertising statement (Norris, Bailey, Bolls & Wise, 2012).

According to Panda and Mishra (2013), non-emotional advertising results in less positive affective reactions, since this type of communication leads consumers to feel less interested and more irritated. Emotional stimuli have been applied in advertising strategies, both of a commercial nature and in the dissemination of messages in the field of health, as a way of persuading public behavior (Dillard & Peck, 2000).

Humorous tone in advertising

Humor, explained both as a practice of men and as a social interaction, tends to be an object of laughter, once associated with something funny (Escalas & Stern, 2003), which can serve a number of purposes, among them, to generate proximity, to overcome obstacles, to reveal lack of commitment to what is said, to provoke, or to appease in situations of tension (Attardo, 1994).

The humorous stimulus is one of the most applied in the advertising communications strategy (Alden, Mukherjee, & Hoyer, 2000), being additionally object of study of several investigations carried out in the last decades (Alden & Hoyer, 1993). When combined with marketing, humor has the capacity of converting advertising into a playful and pleasurable experience (Stern, 1990), suppressing the need for complex thoughts processing (Bishop, 2013). While watching a humorous advertisement, the audience is faced with the need of interpreting the message that is being communicated in an absurd way, reaching its true, non-literal meaning, which leads to a feeling of relief, positive feelings and laughter (Speck, 1990).

Several studies support an association between the element of humor and the positive attitude towards the advertisement (Dinana & El-tazy, 2016; Petrescu, Girona, & Korgaonkar, 2015). Moreover, humor is understood, by theorists, as a publicity element capable of capturing the audience's attention (Cline & Kellaris, 2007).

At the same time, studies that cover humor in advertising, conclude that its cognitive structure increases the memorization of the message (Alden & Hoyer, 1993; Strick, Holland, van Baaren, Knippenberg, & Dijksterhuis, 2009), which is justified by the fact that it provokes a greater number of discussions, and because it is a topic of greater relevance to people, generally resulting in a greater capacity for persuasion (Dunlop, Perez, & Cotter, 2014). Nonetheless, there are also those who consider that humor can divert attention from the main message of the ad to the joke itself, leading to the memorization of information secondary to the benefits of the brand (Eisend, 2001).

Allegedly, one of the most forwarded types of content are humorous ads (Brown, Badhury & Pope, 2010), being humor an element that positively weights on the intention to share them (Petrescu, Girona, & Korgaonkar, 2015). Likewise, ads with humor tend to be more shared and to engage people on social networks, due to the fact that this type of online environment is associated with positive emotions, such as entertainment and free time (Reyes, Rosso, & Buscaldi, 2012).

Despite the linearity in the positive observations about humor in advertising, when compared to drama, divergent findings emerge. As claimed by Miller (2014), although human nature triggers emotional reactions more easily when confronted with drama, people have the tendency to prefer stimuli linked to humor. In a research conducted by Speck (1991), it became clear that humorous ads attract more attention and the attitude towards them is more

positive, towards those who are from another stimulus. Duncan (1979), on the other hand, suggests the humor constitutes a differentiating factor in attention only when the content of the message is boring. With respect to message recall, Sutherland (1982) states that there is no distinction between the humorous and the serious approach, however, according to Badli and Dzulkifli (2013), humorous contents are generally more easily remembered. In terms of ads share, Berger and Milkman (2009) declare that the most fun ads are the ones that people share more easily.

Humorous Threat Persuasion (HTP) is a theory that consists on the application of humor as a way to persuade the audience, when delivering information that suggests some type of threat (Tinkham & Yoon, 2013). The theory has proved that, when approaching a subject that evokes fear and threatening situations, generally associated with health and the environment, humor can be a persuasive weapon (Conway and Dubé, 2002; Yoon & Tinkham, 2013), diminishing defensive responses, and thus increasing the effect of the message (Mukherjee & Dubé, 2012).

In a study conducted by Griese, Alexandrov, Michaelis and Lilly (2018), regarding the effect of humor on pro-environment advertising with comparison between advertising communications based on other stimuli, the humorous ads in test triggered more positive attitudes, greater involvement with the problem, as well as a better attitude towards the ad, in relation to the non-humorous ads. According to O'Neill and Nicholson-Cole (2009), positive feelings are normally more effective when the goal is to promote behaviors that fight climate change, since it removes negative feelings, such as fear and guilt. Furthermore, in the context of social causes communication, the ability of humor to grab the attention of the viewer, as well as to diminish counter-argumentative responses, can be seen as an effective way to make people act (Nabi, Moyer -Gusé, & Byrne, 2007).

Several researches proved that, although commonly understanding the purpose of the message in advertising communications in which fear prevails, people feel hardly motivated to act (Hasting et al., 2004; Brennan & Binney, 2010) or become more involved with the problem when confronted with those (United Nations Environment Program, 2005). There are, however, those who claim existing a link between threatening messages and its effectiveness on influencing public's behavior (Quester & Arthur, 2004).

Conceptual model for the empirical study

In the tab “Measuring the effectiveness of social marketing campaigns” - indicators that can be considered to measure the effectiveness of an advertising campaign integrated in social marketing were discussed. The following figure summarizes the main conclusions regarding this topic and that will be useful for the next empirical part of this study.

	Factor i	Author	Affirmation	
Affective dimension	Attitude towards the ad	Mackenzie, Lutz, e Belch (1986) Edell e Burke (1984)	$effectiveness = k_1 + b_1 attitude + e_1$ $corr(effectiveness, attitude) > 0$	Traditional advertising
Cognitive dimension	Attention	Bezdek e Gerrig (2016) Pieters e Wedel (2011) Rossiter e Percy (2001)	$effectiveness = k_2 + b_2 attention + e_2$ $corr(effectiveness, attention) > 0$	
	Recall	Mehta e Purvis (2006) Brasini, Freo, e Tassinari (2011)	$effectiveness = k_3 + b_3 recall + e_3$ $corr(effectiveness, recall) > 0$	
Behavioural dimension	Intention to forward	Thorbjørnsen et al. (2015)	$effectiveness = k_4 + b_4 iforward + e_4$ $corr(efetividade, iforward) > 0$	Social advertising
	Behavioural intention	Fishbein e Ajzen (1975)	$effectiveness = k_5 + b_5 beavouriali + e_5$ $corr(effectiveness, beavouriali) > 0$	

Figure 1. Systematization of Key Concepts for Measuring the Effectiveness of Social Advertising;

Taking into account the literary review, a conceptual model was elaborated that systematizes the different connections between the variables. The following figure depicts the analyzes carried out in relation to objective 1, focused on humor, and those developed in order to fulfill objective 2 of comparing humor and drama in this context.

Figure 2. Conceptual model of the study of the impact of the humorous tone on the effectiveness factors of a pro-environmental advertisement in a narrative format;

Methodological procedures

The present study is based on two measurement instruments, the questionnaire and the interview, focusing the investigation in both a quantitative and qualitative analysis, respectively.

In a first phase, for the quantitative methodology, a case study was considered, which can be defined as a research methodology focused on the analysis of a phenomenon and its dynamics, taking into account the context in which it is inserted (Yin, 2003). Thus, to ascertain the influence of the element of humor in advertising pieces in a narrative format with an environmental content, viewers were exposed to two videos with two distinct tones - one dramatic ("Greenpeace - Ocean of the Future") and the other humorous ("UN Environment - It's not me, it's you"). Both advertising pieces have a special focus on the issue of consumption of excess disposable plastic, given the extreme current relevance of the theme.

The survey, which revolves around these two videos, comprises a series of measures adapted from different scales created by authors that concern the variables to be analyzed, namely the Attitude towards the advertisement, Attention to the advertisement, Recall of the advertisement, Behavioral intention, and Intention to forward. The measure General effect of humorous tone was designed specifically in the context of this study. The study sample is considered non-probabilistic, as it was selected based on its availability to collaborate in the study. For data collection, the Qualtrics platform was used, and the responses were measured using the IBM Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) statistical program. Then, an observational-type investigation was planned, with descriptive and analytical studies.

In order to meet the main objective outlined for this investigation - to ascertain the influence that the humorous tone has on the effectiveness of an advertising narrative inserted in environmental social marketing -, the quantitative analysis was complemented with interviews with professionals in the area, contributing for a deeper understanding of how consumers perceive humor.

For this study, interviews of a semi-structured nature were considered, that is, made from a previous formulation of questions present in a script, with, however, flexibility for the interviewees to freely discuss the subject (Quivy & Campenhout, 1998). The sample consisted of four art directors from three creative agencies, in total, namely Publicis, Leo Burnett, and ComOn, all with more than a decade of experience in the area, integrating different positions along their professional paths, as directors creatives, Head of art, art direction assistants, among others.

The script, common to all interviews, was created from four distinct thematic blocks: 'Humor in advertising integrated in commercial marketing', 'Humor in advertising integrated in social marketing for the environment', 'Influence of tone on advertising integrated in the context of social marketing for the environment', and 'Humor as a relevant tool in the context of social marketing for the environment'. The analysis of the interviews was made based on a content analysis, comprising two dimensions: the descriptive, which corresponds to the report of what was said by the interviewees, and the interpretative, which lies on the conclusions drawn by the interviewer, trying to interpret the interviewees' words (Guerra, 2006).

Results and discussion

In the context of pro-environmental advertising narratives, is the humorous tone a technique with a positive effect on the effectiveness of an advertising narrative?

Respecting the general rating of the humorous ad made by the respondents, it appears that the advertising was effective in relation to the four factors under study. Thus, when watching the environmental narrative in a humorous tone, the respondents revealed a positive attitude towards it, meaning that, in general, they reacted favorably when confronted with the advertising video. Besides that, they expressed an equally positive intention to share it via online, a general attention of an intense degree, and a good memorization of four important elements of the narrative (table 1 and 2).

Table 1

Summary of Mean and Standard Deviation of Attitude towards the Ad, General Attention and Intention to Forward regarding the humorous ad

Variable	Humorous Ad
	M(SD)
Attitude towards the ad	4.31 (.76)
Impact	4.15 (.91)
Attractiveness	4.23 (.94)
Clarity	4.54 (.74)
General attention	3.84 (.78)
Attention	3.86 (.86)
Engagement	3.83 (.80)
Intention to forward	3.76 (1.13)

Table 2

Frequencies related to Recall regarding the Humorous Ad

Variable	N	%
Recall		84.0
Brand	119	69.2
Main character	156	90.7
Main scenario	169	98.3
Message	134	77.9

Additionally, humor has shown to have a positive effect, both in terms of the ability to alert to the environmental cause, to make the message understood, to make it credible, as well as to attract attention to the essential part of the communication (table 3). These findings indicate how the element of humor prompted the fulfillment of important goals related to the concept of social advertising, essential to influence decision making.

Table 3

Mean and Standard Deviation regarding Effect of Humor

Variable	M (SD)
Effect of humor	4.11 (.76)
Creates alert in relation to the environmental cause.	4.09 (.89)
Contributes for message comprehension.	4.25 (.79)
Makes the message credible.	3.93 (.94)
Attracts attention to the message essential.	4.15 (.94)

According to the interviewees, humor leads people to easily identify with certain everyday situations, as it is an emotion considerably present in interpersonal relationships. Consequently, it constitutes a mechanism that naturally fosters the connections between consumers and what the brands are communicating, by generating a feeling of empathy on the audience. These aspects inherent to the humorous tone can explain the positive attitude revealed by the spectators, in relation to the advertisement.

The humorous tone is also very much associated with entertainment, which creates on the audience the predisposition and desire to watch a video or an ad until the end. This ability of humor to make people concentrate on the content allows it to be a good technique to draw people's attention to the problem, as well as to get the word out. The results of the intention to forward, as well as those related to attention to the problem and general attention, mirror that. The fact that humor in the context of advertising communication with special focus on environmental awareness is something unprecedented, makes people more curious, which is reflected in a good absorption and understanding of the message. In addition, in several interventions, interviewees stated that humor allows people to retain information more easily.

Thus, humor is perceived as a technique with a positive contribution to the effectiveness of an advertising piece with an environmental content. Still, its positive effect will depend on the type of humor applied in the campaign, as well as on the brand that is communicating the humorous content. In addition, for the result to be the effectiveness of the advertising piece, it is necessary to combine this tool with the correct strategy outlined in the phase prior to the execution.

...And can humorous narratives reach the same level, or a higher one, of effectiveness when compared with dramatic narratives?

Regarding the comparison of the evaluations of the two advertising narratives, it appears that the environmental narrative of a dramatic nature was superior to the narrative of a humorous tone in almost all dimensions under study, namely at the level of Attitude towards the advertisement, General attention and Intention to Forward. Concerning recall, the difference is not considered significant (table 5).

Table 4

Summary of the Mean and Standard Deviation of Attitude towards the Ad, General Attention, And Intention to Forward with Comparison between Tone, through Paired Samples Test

Variables	Dramatic ad M (SD)	Humorous ad M (SD)	t
Attitude	4.58 (.55)	4.31 (.76)	4.741***
General attention	4.27 (.91)	3.84 (.78)	3.447**
Intention to forward	3.92 (1.03)	3.76 (1.13)	2.230*

Nota: * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$

Table 5

Mean of Percentages related to Recall of Dramatic and Humorous Ad

Variable	Dramatic ad M%	Humorous ad M%
Recall	74.2	84.0

When it comes to behavioural intention, the outcomes were very positive ($M = 4.21 \pm .93$). Even more relevant is the fact that, among those who demonstrated a positive behavioural intention, the vast majority agreed on how both ads positively impacted that intention. In addition, about 64.5% of those who felt influenced by the ads, stated that the dramatic ad influenced in a higher degree, comparatively with the other (figure 3).

Figure 3. Influence of the ads on the Behavioural intention;

Taking into account the significant results obtained from the statistical analysis, the conceptual model was redesigned (Figure 7).

Figure 4. Representative scheme of the results obtained from the quantitative analysis.
 Note: M: Average; %: Percentage; Average%: average of the percentages

In agreement with the art directors, emotional advertisements evoke greater cognitive processing, so if an advertising piece is capable of provoking an emotional response, it will easily generate recall, which may justify the level of recall shown with the two pieces .

The fact that the dramatic tone ad had a greater impact on the respondents' behavioural intention, when compared to the humorous tone ad, can be explained by the fact that the effectiveness of a campaign being related to factors other than the tone of communication, such as the choice insight, or another aspect of creative development. The lightness of the humor leads to the creation of a lower distancing from the problem, which, on the one hand, may justify the fact that the humorous video has not been so great at capturing the real urgency of the problem. However, there were those who stated that this less distance from the issue can also contribute to a greater involvement with the problem, thus constituting an incentive to fight it.

Final considerations

This study seeks to provide knowledge related to the effectiveness of strategies related to advertising narratives in favor of the environment, since storytelling as an advertising approach has been a topic of general interest, both among theorists and at a practical level, and given the current urgency to act in an environmental way.

This investigation approached the humorous tone as a factor influencing the success of environmental advertising narratives, being the study of this effect applied to a specific context - the case of the comparison of the campaign “#CleanSeas Break-Up PSA: “It's not me, it's you. ”, publicized by the UN Environment brand, with the “Ocean of the future” campaign, publicized by Greenpeace. In particular, the objectives of this study were, first, to understand whether humor has the potential to exert a positive influence in the context of advertising narratives in favor of the environment; second, for ascertaining, between a dramatic and a humorous advertising narrative, the most effective one.

It is not possible to verify that humor contributes more positively to the success of an environmental campaign, given the superiority of the dramatic narrative over the humorous, in this specific study. However, it can be concluded that the humorous tone is a tool capable of making a positive contribution in the area of social advertising and should therefore be considered. It appears that, although apparently contradictory at first, humor can be associated with a positive Attitude towards the advertisement, General attention, Intention to forward and Recall. It was found that, in this particular case, humor had the capacity to create alert in relation to the environmental cause, to make the message understood, to make it more credible, and to attract attention to what was essential in the advertising communication. The entertainment factor and the fact that it is an easily related emotion are points in favor for development of empathy with the content, as well as of the attention and dissemination of the message.

Even so, it is important to bear in mind that, for an environmental awareness campaign of this type to succeed, the choice of insight is an aspect that will weigh on the outcomes, as well as the type of humor and the brand that is trying to get heard. If these elements are not selected in an accurate and proper manner, there is no tone that can save the campaign and make it effective.

This information constitutes relevant data for the scientific community, as well as for creatives and entrepreneurs, who seek to create and implement advertising narratives in favor of environmental causes. The model created at the end of the study, based on the results obtained, mirrors the main data extracted from the quantitative research, constituting an important theoretical contribution in this area. For creatives and entrepreneurs, it should be noted that, despite the drama being a valid and persuasive approach in the context of environmental advertising, there are other paths that environmental campaigns can take.

With regard to the limitations of this investigation, the fact that the sampling method for the questionnaire is non-probabilistic, implies that the sample will hardly mirror the inhabitants of Portugal with realism. In addition, the sample is not very balanced in terms of the gender of the participants, since about 18% are male and 82% are female. Another limitation is the fact that only two advertising pieces were selected, which makes it difficult to generalize the tone effect.

Social advertising constitutes a field with so many factors, of personality and context, that play against each other, that other domains could have been explored, in addition to what was studied in this investigation. It is considered pertinent that future studies that address this same theme have as object of study several pieces, with different types of humor or with the same style of humor, depending on the purpose of the investigation, so that the generalization of the results is more accurate. At the same time, other studies may consider moderating effects, such as the impact of the brand that is communicating, or the cultural effect of the subjects.

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